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TEACHING CRITICAL THINKING IN BUSINESS ENGLISH FOR ACADEMIC PURPOSES

Karimov Feruzjon Alisher o'g'li

TESL/TEFL Trainer

Webster university Allumnie

Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and
Agricultural Mechanization Engineers (TIAME)

National Research University EFL Teacher

karimovferuzshoh@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Critical thinking is a fundamental skill for students pursuing Business English for Academic Purposes (BEAP). This study examines the role of critical thinking in BEAP, exploring methods to enhance this skill and its impact on students' academic and professional success. Through a mixed-methods approach, we investigate the effectiveness of specific pedagogical strategies in fostering critical thinking among BEAP learners. The quantitative survey conducted with 150 students revealed that while a majority recognize the importance of critical thinking, there is a significant gap in their confidence levels to apply these skills. Additionally, qualitative interviews with 20 instructors highlighted effective strategies such as case studies, group discussions, and reflective writing, along with challenges including language barriers and varying levels of prior knowledge. The study concludes that integrating targeted critical thinking activities into BEAP curricula and providing necessary support can significantly enhance students' analytical abilities, preparing them for future academic and professional challenges.

Key Words: *critical thinking, Business English, academic purposes, pedagogical strategies, language barriers.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Критическое мышление является фундаментальным навыком для студентов, изучающих деловой английский язык для академических целей (BEAP). В данном исследовании рассматривается роль критического мышления в BEAP, исследуются методы улучшения этого навыка и его влияние на академический и профессиональный успех студентов. Используя смешанный

методический подход, мы исследуем эффективность конкретных педагогических стратегий по развитию критического мышления у студентов ВЕАР. Количественный опрос, проведенный среди 150 студентов, показал, что, хотя большинство признают важность критического мышления, существует значительный разрыв в уровне их уверенности в применении этих навыков. Кроме того, качественные интервью с 20 преподавателями выявили эффективные стратегии, такие как кейс-стади, групповые обсуждения и рефлексивное письмо, а также трудности, включая языковые барьеры и различные уровни предварительных знаний. Исследование заключает, что интеграция целенаправленных мероприятий по развитию критического мышления в учебные программы ВЕАР и предоставление необходимой поддержки могут значительно улучшить аналитические способности студентов, подготавливая их к будущим академическим и профессиональным вызовам.

Ключевые слова: критическое мышление, деловой английский, академические цели, педагогические стратегии, языковые барьеры.

АБСТРАКТ

Танқидий фикрлаш, академик мақсадлар учун бизнес инглиз тилини ўрганаётган талабалар учун асосий кўникма ҳисобланади. Ушбу тадқиқотда танқидий фикрлашнинг ВЕАРдаги ўрни ўрганилади, ушбу кўникмани ривожлантириш усуллари ва унинг талабаларнинг академик ва профессионал муваффақиятига таъсири таҳлил қилинади. Аралаш методик ёндашув орқали биз ВЕАР ўқувчиларининг танқидий фикрлаш кўникмасини ривожлантиришида аниқ педагогик стратегияларнинг самарадорлигини ўрганамиз. 150 талабадан ташкил топган миқдорий сўровномалар шуни кўрсатдики, кўпчилик танқидий фикрлашнинг аҳамиятини тан олса-да, ушбу кўникмаларни қўллашда ишонч даражасида сезиларли фарқ бор. Шунингдек, 20 нафар ўқитувчи билан ўтказилган сифатли суҳбатлар кейс-стади, гуруҳли муҳокамалар ва рефлексив ёзиш каби самарали стратегияларни, шунингдек, тил тўсиқлари ва турли даражадаги олдинги билимлар каби қийинчиликларни аниқлади. Тадқиқот натижасида ВЕАР ўқув дастурларига танқидий фикрлаш фаолиятларини киритиш ва зарур қўллаб-қувватлашни таъминлаш талабаларнинг таҳлилий қобилиятларини сезиларли даражада ошириши мумкинлигини кўрсатди, уларни келгусидаги академик ва профессионал муаммоларга тайёрлайди.

Калит сўзлар: танқидий фикрлаш, бизнес инглиз тили, академик мақсадлар, педагогик стратегиялар, тил тўсиқлари.

INTRODUCTION

Critical thinking is an essential skill for students engaged in Business English for Academic Purposes (BEAP), playing a pivotal role in their academic and future professional success. In the context of BEAP, students must navigate complex business concepts and communicate effectively in English, making critical thinking an indispensable tool. This skill enables students to analyze information, evaluate arguments, and make informed decisions, which are crucial capabilities in the business world (Miller, 2020).

However, fostering critical thinking in BEAP presents unique challenges. The dual focus on language proficiency and business knowledge can make it difficult for students to develop critical thinking skills. Additionally, language barriers and varying levels of prior knowledge among students can hinder their ability to engage in critical analysis and discussion (Nguyen, 2021).

Teaching English for Academic Purposes (EAP) in a business context with an emphasis on critical thinking involves integrating business-specific content with language instruction, using methods that promote analytical and evaluative skills. Effective pedagogical strategies include the use of case studies, which provide real-world business scenarios for students to analyze and solve, enhancing their practical and critical thinking skills (Thompson, 2022). Group discussions and debates on business topics encourage students to articulate their thoughts, consider diverse perspectives, and defend their viewpoints, further honing their critical thinking abilities (Garcia, 2020).

Moreover, reflective writing assignments enable students to introspect on their learning experiences and articulate their thought processes, thereby deepening their understanding and ability to critically evaluate information (Harris, 2019). These strategies not only improve language proficiency but also equip students with the critical thinking skills necessary for academic research and professional decision-making in a business context.

This study aims to explore the importance of critical thinking in BEAP, identify effective teaching strategies to enhance this skill, and address the challenges faced by both students and instructors. By understanding these dynamics, educators can better prepare students for the demands of academic and professional environments, ensuring they possess the analytical and evaluative skills necessary for success (Walker, 2017).

METHODS

To investigate the role of critical thinking in Business English for Academic Purposes (BEAP), we employed a mixed-methods approach. This approach combined quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of both students' and instructors' perspectives across several European institutions.

1. Quantitative Survey:

- Participants: We conducted a survey with 150 BEAP students from five universities in Europe, including institutions in the United Kingdom, Germany, France, Italy, and Spain. The participants were selected to ensure a diverse representation of students with varying levels of English proficiency and business knowledge.

- Survey Design: The survey included a series of Likert-scale and open-ended questions designed to gauge students' perceptions of critical thinking, their confidence in applying these skills, and the perceived impact on their academic performance. Specific questions focused on their experiences with different pedagogical strategies, such as case studies, group discussions, and reflective writing.

- Data Collection: Surveys were distributed electronically via university email systems and were available in both English and the native language of each country to ensure clarity and accessibility.

- Data Analysis: Responses were analyzed using statistical software to identify trends and correlations. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, while inferential statistics (such as t-tests and ANOVA) were employed to compare responses across different groups (e.g., by country or proficiency level).

2. Qualitative Interviews:

- Participants: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 20 BEAP instructors from the same five European universities. Instructors were selected based on their experience teaching BEAP courses and their willingness to participate in the study.

- Interview Guide: The interview questions were designed to explore instructors' perspectives on teaching critical thinking, the effectiveness of different strategies, and the challenges they face. Topics included the use of case studies, group discussions, reflective writing, and the impact of language barriers and prior knowledge on students' critical thinking development.

- Data Collection: Interviews were conducted via video conferencing software and recorded with participants' consent. Each interview lasted approximately 45 minutes.

- **Data Analysis:** Interview transcripts were analyzed using thematic analysis. Key themes and patterns were identified, coded, and categorized to understand common challenges and successful strategies. NVivo software was used to assist in managing and analyzing qualitative data.

Data Triangulation: To enhance the validity and reliability of the findings, data from the quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews were triangulated. This process involved comparing and contrasting the quantitative and qualitative data to identify consistent themes and discrepancies. Triangulation helped provide a more comprehensive understanding of the role of critical thinking in BEAP and the effectiveness of various pedagogical approaches across different European contexts.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval was obtained from each participating university's ethics committee. All participants were informed about the purpose of the study, their right to confidentiality, and their ability to withdraw at any time without penalty. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection.

RESULTS

The results of this study provide insights into the perceptions of BEAP students and instructors regarding critical thinking, the effectiveness of various pedagogical strategies, and the challenges faced in fostering critical thinking skills. Data from the quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews are presented below, highlighting key findings across the five European universities involved in the study.

1. Quantitative Survey Results:

- **Student Perceptions of Critical Thinking:**

- A significant majority (85%) of the 150 students surveyed recognized the importance of critical thinking in their BEAP studies. However, only 60% of students felt confident in their ability to apply critical thinking skills effectively.

- Students from the UK and Germany reported higher levels of confidence (68% and 65%, respectively) compared to their counterparts in Italy and Spain (55% and 50%, respectively), indicating a possible influence of educational background on confidence levels.

- **Effectiveness of Pedagogical Strategies:**

- Students rated case studies (78%), group discussions (74%), and reflective writing (70%) as the most effective strategies for developing critical thinking skills.

These activities were particularly appreciated for their practical application and interactive nature.

- French students showed a strong preference for group discussions (82%), whereas German students found case studies (85%) particularly beneficial. Reflective writing was rated highly across all countries, with the highest appreciation in the UK (75%).

- Impact on Academic Performance:

- Students who frequently engaged in critical thinking activities reported higher academic performance. Approximately 65% of students who regularly participated in case studies and group discussions indicated improved grades and a better understanding of business concepts.

- A correlation analysis revealed a positive relationship between the frequency of critical thinking activities and self-reported academic performance ($r = 0.48, p < 0.01$).

2. Qualitative Interview Results:

- Instructor Perspectives on Teaching Critical Thinking:

- Instructors universally acknowledged the importance of critical thinking in BEAP and emphasized its role in preparing students for professional challenges. They highlighted the need for integrating critical thinking into the curriculum through various pedagogical strategies.

- Case studies were noted as highly effective by 18 out of 20 instructors, particularly for their ability to simulate real-world business problems and encourage practical application of theoretical knowledge. One instructor from Germany mentioned, "Case studies bridge the gap between theory and practice, helping students to think critically and make informed decisions."

- Challenges in Fostering Critical Thinking:

- Language barriers were a significant challenge, particularly for non-native English speakers. Instructors from Spain and Italy reported that students often struggled with the complex language used in critical thinking activities, which hindered their ability to fully engage.

- Varying levels of prior knowledge also posed a challenge. Instructors noted that students with a strong background in business concepts were more adept at critical thinking, while those with less experience found it more difficult to participate meaningfully.

- Effective Strategies and Recommendations:

- Reflective writing was highlighted as a valuable tool for deepening students' understanding and encouraging introspection. An instructor from the UK stated, "Reflective writing assignments allow students to process what they've learned and develop their critical thinking skills in a structured manner."

- Group discussions were praised for fostering collaborative learning and exposing students to diverse perspectives. However, instructors noted the need for careful facilitation to ensure all students participated and benefited from the discussions.

Comparison Across Countries:

- The study found notable differences in the effectiveness and preference for critical thinking activities across the five countries. For instance, while German students excelled with case studies, French students thrived in group discussions. These differences underscore the importance of adapting teaching strategies to the specific needs and preferences of students in different educational contexts.

Summary of Key Findings:

- Critical thinking is widely recognized as essential in BEAP, but there is a gap between recognition and confidence in applying these skills.

- Pedagogical strategies such as case studies, group discussions, and reflective writing are effective in enhancing critical thinking, though their impact varies by country.

- Language barriers and varying levels of prior knowledge are significant challenges that need to be addressed to foster critical thinking more effectively.

- Tailoring strategies to specific educational contexts and providing additional support can enhance the development of critical thinking skills in BEAP students.

DISCUSSION

The discussion section interprets the results of the study in the context of existing literature, identifies implications for practice, and offers recommendations for future research. The key points discussed are as follows:

1. Importance of Critical Thinking in BEAP:

The findings confirm the widely acknowledged importance of critical thinking in BEAP. Students and instructors alike recognize its value in preparing students for academic success and professional advancement in the business world. The study adds

empirical evidence to the existing literature on the significance of critical thinking in language education and underscores its relevance in the context of BEAP.

2. Effectiveness of Pedagogical Strategies:

The study identifies case studies, group discussions, and reflective writing as effective pedagogical strategies for fostering critical thinking in BEAP. These findings align with previous research highlighting the benefits of active learning approaches in promoting critical thinking skills. However, the study also reveals variations in the effectiveness and preference for these strategies across different European countries, suggesting the need for context-specific approaches in teaching critical thinking.

3. Challenges and Recommendations:

The discussion highlights the challenges faced in fostering critical thinking in BEAP, including language barriers and varying levels of prior knowledge among students. To address these challenges, the study recommends tailored interventions such as language support programs and scaffolding complex concepts. Additionally, instructors are encouraged to adopt inclusive teaching practices that accommodate diverse learner backgrounds and preferences.

4. Implications for Practice:

The findings have several implications for practice in BEAP instruction. Educators should prioritize the integration of critical thinking activities into the curriculum and provide adequate support to students, particularly those facing language barriers. Training programs for instructors should focus on equipping them with the necessary pedagogical skills to facilitate critical thinking development effectively. Moreover, collaboration between language and content instructors can enhance the integration of language and critical thinking instruction in BEAP courses.

5. Limitations and Future Research:

The discussion acknowledges the limitations of the study, including the focus on European contexts and the relatively small sample size. Future research could explore the effectiveness of critical thinking interventions in diverse cultural and linguistic contexts and investigate the long-term impact of critical thinking instruction on students' academic and professional outcomes. Additionally, studies examining the role of technology-mediated learning environments in fostering critical thinking in BEAP could provide valuable insights for practice.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study illuminates the crucial role of critical thinking in Business English for Academic Purposes (BEAP) and underscores the significance of integrating effective pedagogical strategies to foster this skill. The findings demonstrate that while students and instructors recognize the importance of critical thinking, there exists a gap between recognition and confidence in applying these skills. Nevertheless, pedagogical approaches such as case studies, group discussions, and reflective writing emerge as valuable tools for enhancing critical thinking in BEAP, although their effectiveness may vary across different educational contexts.

The study highlights challenges such as language barriers and varying levels of prior knowledge, underscoring the need for tailored interventions and inclusive teaching practices. By addressing these challenges and implementing evidence-based strategies, educators can better prepare BEAP students for academic success and professional excellence in the global business landscape.

Moving forward, future research should explore the effectiveness of critical thinking interventions in diverse cultural and linguistic settings and investigate the long-term impact of critical thinking instruction on students' academic and professional outcomes. Additionally, studies examining the role of technology-mediated learning environments in fostering critical thinking in BEAP could provide valuable insights for practice.

Overall, by embracing a holistic approach to teaching critical thinking in BEAP and collaborating across disciplines, educators can empower students with the analytical and evaluative skills necessary to thrive in the dynamic and competitive world of business.

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